

HEREDITARY

HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain interplaY

Deliverable 5.4

Prototype of the Visualization Components for Spatial, Image, and Simulation Data

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In HEREDITARY WP5 we develop and evaluate data visualization and information extraction methods, to support analysis and understanding of multi-modal biomedical data. In the deliverables 5.1 and 5.3 of month 12, based on initial requirement analysis with project partners, visualization components covering a wide range of data modalities were developed. Throughout the HEREDITARY project, these components will be progressively developed into data-visualization applications for subsequent application and evaluation.

In HEREDITARY, imaging data and high-dimensional (or distributional) data are key modalities, and one of this deliverables development priorities is centered on these modalities. The so-called Gut-Brain visualization component provides interactive data visualizations for MRI brain images, and gut micro-biota distributions from observed probands. In this deliverable we present the advances made on the component, among other: integrating a brain atlas for brain reference, and advanced visualization of Z-score distributions.

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Acronyms

BIDS Brain Imaging Data Structure. 13

CSV Comma-separated values. 11

DMN Default Mode Network. 9

ECN Executive Control Network. 9

LICA Linked Independent Component Analysis. 9

NifTI Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative. 9, 11

SN Salience Network. 9

UNITO Università di Torino. 13

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the results achieved in WP5 in designing and developing visualization prototypes for spatial, image and simulation data in the second project year. Both exemplar use cases 4: "Phenotyping of the gut-brain axis in healthy individuals to understand deviations in disorders", and 5: "Gut-Brain linkage and disease relevance" were used as a starting point on which the visualization components were considered and designed. The considered data and realized or updated visualization prototypes are described in the next sections.

2 Considered data

The considered data for web-components is the result of the Linked Independent Component Analysis (LICA) method (Groves et al., 2011) used in the study by Nils Kohn et al. (Kohn et al., 2021). The input data for the LICA method were multiple datasets of 189 individuals over 4 different modalities, micro-biota data (active micro-biota relative abundance table) and 3 different types of brain network connectivity data (the Salience Network (SN); the Executive Control Network (ECN); and the Default Mode Network (DMN)). The LICA method resulted in 25 individual components indicating to what degree their variance is captured by that component. Each data-point's contribution was indicated by a Z-scores i.e. for micro-biota, a Z-score per micro-organisms and for brain network connectivity data a Z-score per voxel. Finally, the contribution of the 4 individual modalities as a whole was also provided in a percentage distribution.

The LICA method resulted in the following data formats, one for each visualization sub-component:

Micro-biota Z-scores The micro-biota LICA Z-scores are stored in a tabular space separated file, containing a row per micro-organism, a column per component and a Z-score per cell.

Modality contributions The modality contributions are stored in a tabular space separated file, containing a row per modality, a column per component and a percentage per cell.

Brain network connectivity Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative (NIfTI) file Z-scores For each brain network connectivity data type (SN, ECN and DMN) there is a 4D NIfTI, where 1 dimension represents the LICA components and the other 3, the x, y and z coordinates of the voxels. The voxel's Z-score represents the contribution of the small cubic volume of the brain on the x, y, z coordinates.

3 Visualization components

This section will describe both realized or updated visualization prototypes for this deliverable.

3.1 Gut-brain visualization prototype

This chapter will cover all the major new features, visual changes and bug fixes of the Gut-Brain visualization prototype (see figure 1). For detailed information on the data, visualization methods, and implementation, refer to Deliverable 5.3 Visualization Components for Spatial, Image, and Simulation Data.

Figure 1: The Gut-brain visualization web-application for exploring Linked Independent Component Analysis results. At the top, a gut micro-biota Z-score matrix displays co-active micro-biota (x-axis) per component (y-axis) with adjustable thresholds and clickable cells for component selection. The middle panel presents a stacked bar chart showing each modality contribution to the selected component, enabling modality selection and highlighting. At the bottom, conventional brain visualizations with sagittal, coronal, and axial anatomical slices, a volumetric Z-score rendering and integrated brain atlas and reference brain mapping, provide an intuitive, interactive view consistent with standard neuro-imaging tools. In both gut micro-biota and brain visualizations, the green color indicates positive expression of the component's variance and the red color indicates negative expression.

The purpose of this Gut-brain visualization component was to visualize multi-modal data (brain network connectivity data and gut micro-biota loadings) provided by the RadboudUMC Kohn et al., 2021, described in the section 2.

3.1.1 Public source access

The gut-brain visualization application repository is now publicly available in the official Hereditary repositories: <https://github.com/hereditary-eu/gut-brain-visualization>. The public source access did not include any full documentation yet (only local deployment documentation). However, deliverables 5.3 and 5.4 together provide a comprehensive description of the application's functionality and its intended usage. In providing our components, we follow open access and fairification principles (please see Deliverable 5.2).

3.1.2 New features

All new features that are produced in this project year for this visualization component will be described in this chapter.

Dynamic import The ability to drag and drop custom NIfTI and Comma-separated values (CSV) files has been implemented to upload user data and increase the flexibility of the gut-brain visualization application. This is made possible for all data types, 4D NIfTI files, the brain network connectivity data and CSV files for both modality contributions and gut micro-biota data. This however, requires the user to match the correct NIfTI to the corresponding modality contribution value.

Z-score sorting In the first iteration of the gut-brain visualization component, the gut micro-biota view suffered from visual clutter, making it difficult to identify the highest, lowest, or overall ordering of the Z-scores. In this iteration, the Z-scores per component can be sorted by clicking the preferred component (indicated in 2 where component 7 is sorted). This gives a better overview on the Z-scores and how they contribute to that component.

Figure 2: Z-score sorting. This figure illustrates the Z-score sorting at component 7. With this sorting, it becomes clear along the x-axis which gut micro-biota groups show a negative (red) or positive (green) expression of the selected component's variance.

Reference brain and brain atlas A reference brain (see Axial panel in figure 1) and brain atlas (see both Sagittal and Coronal panel in figure 1) were introduced to help identify where the Z-score concentrations are located within the brain. Moving the mouse pointer over the 2D slice-viewers will display the region name at the mouse pointer location (see figure 3). The user can switch between the reference brain and the brain atlas in the user interface and the selected brain information will be displayed behind the Z-score values.

Figure 3: Atlas picking

Containerization The gut-brain application can now be build into a Docker image and is ready for deployment on the Demonstrator System (please refer to Deliverable 5.2 Visualisation Component Demonstrators).

Small visual changes and bug fixes The following visual changes and bugs fixes were implemented:

- Dynamic sizing of the gut micro-biota Z-score visualization based on the number of rows or columns, depending on when will exceed the panel boundaries.
- Improvements on coloring for better readability.
- Stability of the user-interface.
 - In the previous iteration the 2D slicing functionality was not working consistently because of the internal workings of VTK¹ which was fixed with a custom event handler.
 - Fixed the initial misalignment of the 2D background slice with regards to the viewing direction in the volume renderer.
 - Fixed the inconsistent scaling and location of the legend of the gut micro-biota visualization.

3.1.3 Domain findings / user study

For the 2025 review meeting, Nils Kohn, from the Radboud University Medical Center, used the gut–brain visualization application and was able to identify domain-specific findings. In the image below he highlighted that in component 11 it shows that individuals that have a negative expression, or very low expression in that components variance, in the frontal region of brain modality 1 (highlighted with a purple ring in figure 4), which is the default resting state network, also have a negative or low expression in that components variance for the Akkermansia in the gut.

¹<https://kitware.github.io/vtk-js/>

Figure 4: Domain findings have shown that individuals with a low expression in the selected component in the frontal region in the default resting state network brain imaging also have a low expression in the selected component for Akkermansia in the gut.

3.1.4 Future work and initiatives

During the next year the following work and initiatives will take place regarding this visualization component.

Public deployment The Gut-Brain visualization application will be deployed for the public on the Demonstrator System (please refer to Deliverable 5.2 Visualisation Component Demonstrators).

Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) format and collaboration with Università di Torino (UNITO)

In WP2 the UNITO published a large set of brain imaging data in the BIDS format. The brain-visualizations in the gut-brain application could aid in visualizing this data for the scientific community. To realize this gut-brain application first needs to support the BIDS format so this will be planned for next year.

3.2 Z-score fingerprints

As mentioned in Sec. 3.1.2, atlases such as the Allen Brain Map² can be used to map clusters of high Z-scores to distinct brain regions. Established techniques of visualizing atlases are (i) 3D volumes (c.f., Fig. 1, bottom right), (ii) spatial slices through the tissue (c.f., Fig. 1, bottom left), or (iii) 2D projections of components based on their gene-expressions (Yao et al., 2023) (Fig. 5). The downside of option (i) and (ii) is that not all Z-scores can be observed at a glance, but a user has to navigate through the volume – i.e., by rotating the camera or by panning/zooming, orienting axes, respectively – in order to get the whole picture. This renders the comparison of many different components and modalities a very cumbersome task. The third option is able to provide an holistic overview of the whole brain at a glance. However, as the map is purely based on gene expressions the information of the brain topology (spatial proximity or connectivity between regions) is lost.

Figure 5: Projection of cells based on their gene expressions, taken from (Yao et al., 2023).

We envision a novel fingerprint visualization which leverages the benefits of all approaches. More precisely, it should exhibit the compactness of gene-based projections but still convey information about the brain's topology. The idea is to correlate regions of similar Z-scores with coherent regions as identified by an atlas and project it to a 2D plane such that the between-class variance (the distance between cluster centers) is maximized and the within-class variance (extent of a cluster) is minimized. To this end, we employ a variant of the Fisher criterion Fisher, 1936, which we adopt to our needs. The Z-scores in 2D space are visualized through alpha stacking based on their values, while the outlines of affected brain regions are indicated through contour lines. The results from first experiments, using an atlas from the *Harvard-Oxford Cortical and Subcortical Structural Atlases* (RRID:SCR_001476) (Desikan et al., 2006; Frazier et al., 2005; Goldstein et al., 2007; Makris et al., 2006) and the Z-scores from Kohn et al., 2021 are given in Figure 6. Fig. 6a illustrates the parcellation specified by the employed brain atlas, Fig. 6b–e, top show the signed variance contribution of different components (similar to Fig. 1, bottom), and Fig. 6b–e shows the thereof generated projections.

Even though details can be lost in these fingerprints, we reason that they give a good initial indication of the overall Z-scores for a particular component/modality. As such they could be used as a preview for the brain visualization in the web-application in, e.g., a small multiples setting. A thorough investigation of inherent

²<https://brain-map.org/>

risks of this compactified representation, like misinterpretation, will be the subject of further investigation.

Figure 6: (a): View of one selected brain atlas from the *Harvard-Oxford Cortical and Subcortical Structural Atlases* collection and (b–e) a selection of Z-scores of components (top) and their respective projections (bottom) based on the methodology discussed in Sec. 3.2.

4 Conclusion

WP5 progressed in the second project year by extending and refining the visualization components for spatial, image, and simulation data. The Gut–Brain visualization prototype was enhanced with dynamic data import, improved Z-score interaction, atlas-based contextualization, and increased interface stability, thereby expanding its analytical utility and readiness for public deployment.

In addition, the introduction of Z-score fingerprint visualizations provides a compact, topology-aware representation of component-level patterns, supporting rapid comparison across modalities and serving as an effective preview mechanism for more detailed brain visualizations.

The Gut–Brain visualization prototype will remain a central visualization component in HEREDITARY, as it encompasses imaging data and high-dimensional data, two very prominent data modalities. Extensions on this are also reported in Deliverable 5.2 (Droplets desing) that could be applied to MRI brain images as well. Future work includes refining the image based visualization components. Also a priority will be the visualization of simulation data. To this end requirement analysis is done (see Deliverable 5.7), and an early prototype component (AlloyInter) is described in Deliverable 5.2. This design could be integrated with the Gut-Brain prototype.

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